

Analysis Of Rainfall Pattern For Lower Damanganga River Basin Of Gujarat

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Abstract— The availability of water for any river basin forms the basis for the planning and management of the water resources for hydraulic structures. It is essential to carry out the analysis of change in the rainfall pattern in a basin to access the availability of water after construction of major hydraulic structures.

The Damanganga basin is one of the major river basins of Gujarat and is located in the southern Gujarat. The Damanganga basin has two major hydraulic structures namely Madhuban dam and Vapi weir. This paper attempts to analyse the rainfall pattern in the lower Damanganga basin. The results of the study can be utilized to check the possibility of availability of water for further use.

Keywords—Average Depth, Probability, Rainfall, Return Period.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Damanganga originates from Sahyadri hills near Valveri village in Paint taluka of Nasik district in Maharashtra State. It travels a distance of 131.30 km. before it drains to Arabian Sea at Daman Damanganga alongwith its tributories mainly flows through the hilly areas of Mahashtra, Gujarat and Union Territory Dadara and Nagar Haweli and Daman. The major tributories of the Damanganga River are Dawan, Shrimant, Val, Rayate, Lendi, Wagh, Sakartond, Roshni, Dudhni, and Piperiya. The basin is situated between 19° 51' to 20° 28' North latitude and 72° 50' to 73° 38' East. Longitude. The total drainage area of the basin is 2318 sq.km. The style will adjust your fonts and line spacing. Do not

change the font sizes or line spacing to squeeze more text into a limited number of pages. Use italics for emphasis; do not underline.

II. CLIMATE

The entire Damanganga Basin lies in the western ghat region. It is bounded on the west by Arabian Sea and on the east by Sahyadri ranges. The climate of the basin is characterised by a hot summer, which is generally dry except the southwest monsoon during June to September.

The basin receives most of the rainfall from the south west monsoon during June to September Average annual rainfall of the basin is about 2200 mm.

A. Major project

The important project of the basin is Damanganga project. The Madhuban Dam is a composite dam constructed across the river Damanganga near village Madhuban of Dharampur Taluka, Valsad district of Gujarat state. The main purpose of the project is irrigation, other being water supply for domestic and industrial use and for generation of 2.0 MW of power. The project has a network of canal system on either bank of the river to provide irrigation to an area of 56630 hectares of lands. The dam has height of 50 m above the deepest foundation to store 567Mm³ of water. Figure 1 shows the Damanganga basin and location of Madhuban Dam.

B. Figure 1 Damanganga River Basin

III. DATA COLLECTION

For the purpose of this study, the rainfall data was collected for seven raingauge stations located in the lower Damanganga basin between Madhuban dam site and the Vapi weir site. The data was obtained from State Water Data Centre. Table 1 shows the details for the locations of the seven raingauge stations

A. Locations of raingauge stations in lower Damanganga basin

Station Name	Latitude	Longitude
Bhilad	201618	725241
Kelavani	201510	725500
Khanvel	200726	730422
Madhuban Dam	201306	730238
Naroli	201613	725540
Silvassa	201740	730130
Vapi Bridge	202019	725431

The locations of the raingauge stations were plotted on using Google Earth. Figure 2 shows the locations of the raingauges in the lower Damanganga basin.

Figure 2 locations of the raingauges in the lower Damanganga basin.

The individual analysis of the rainfall pattern was carried out for all the raingauges for the annual rainfall values.

The results for the analysis are shown in the figures 3(a to g).

Figure 3 (a) Analysis for Madhuban raingauge

Figure 3 (b) Analysis for Khanvel raingauge

Figure 3 (c) Analysis for Naroli raingauge

Figure 3 (d) Analysis for silvasa raingauge

Figure 3 (e) Analysis for Vapi bridge raingauge

Figure 3 (f) Analysis for Bhilad raingauge

Figure 3 (g) Analysis for Kelavani raingauge

The trend analysis for individual raingauge stations shows an increasing trend for all stations except Kelavani raingauge station. Table 2 shows the results for the rainfall pattern analysis for the individual raingauge stations in the lower Damanganga basin.

Rain gauge stations	Average Rainfall (mm)	Max. rainfall (mm) (occurrence year)	Min. rainfall (mm) (occurrence year)
Naroli	1995	2754 (2005)	1520 (2012)
Madhuban	2108	3336 (1994)	1263 (1987)
Khanvel	2171	3244 (1994)	1336 (1987)
Silvasa	2273	3564 (1994)	1140 (1997)
Vapi	2138	2911 (1995)	1039 (1987)

IV. COMPUTING AVERAGE DEPTH OF RAINFALL

The jpeg image of the Damanganga basin obtained from the office of Madhuban dam was geo referenced using QGIS software. The geo-referenced basin map was then superimposed on the locations of the raingauges using Google Earth. This map was then used to separate the lower Damanganga river basin to separate the study area. Figure 4 shows the location of the lower Damanganga basin.

Figure 4 Lower Damanganga basin

The isolated area of the lower Damanganga river basin was used for construction of the Thiessen polygons for computation of average depth of rainfall.

V. THIESSEN POLYGON METHOD

In this method the rainfall recorded at each station is given a weightage on the basis of an area closest to the station. This

Name of Rain gauge station	Catchment Area of rain gauge station
Vapi weir	148 sq.km
Silvasa	66 sq.km
Naroli	56 sq.km
Madhuban dam	129 sq.km
Khanvel	98 sq.km

method gives the effective result. Once the wei

ghtage factor is determined, the calculation of average rainfall is computed using the following formula.

$$\bar{P} = \frac{P_1A_1 + P_2A_2 + \dots + P_nA_n}{(A_1 + A_2 + \dots + A_n)}$$

where, P₁, P₂, ..P_n are the precipitations for the raingauge stations and A₁, A₂, ... A_n are the areas for the respective polygons. Figure 5 (a) shows the construction of the Thiessen's polygons and Figure 5 (b) shows the areas considered for each raingauge station.

Figure 5 (a) & (b) Thiessen's Polygon

Table 3 shows the areas enclosed for each raingauge station

Table 3 Area covered by each raingauge

Table 4 shows the average depth of rainfall computed using Thiessen's polygon method.

Table 4 Average Depth of Rainfall

Year	Average Depth of Rainfall (mm)	Year	Average Depth of Rainfall
1986	2075	2001	1948
1987	1473	2002	1878
1988	3032	2003	2357
1989	1883	2004	2530
1990	2007	2005	2721
1991	2010	2006	2544
1992	2157	2007	2598
1993	2449	2008	2222
1994	3379	2009	1719

1995	1531	2010	2467
1996	1165	2011	2208
1997	1675	2012	1493
1998	2003	2013	2906
1999	1642	2014	2278
2000	2003		

The probability analysis was carried out for the average annual rainfall and the return periods were computed for various values. Table 5 shows the results for the probability analysis and the return periods for the various storms.

VI. GUMBEL DISTRIBUTION

Gumbel distribution is one of the most widely used probability distribution functions for extreme values in hydrologic and meteorologic studies for prediction of maximum Rainfall. According to this theory, the probability of occurrence of an event equal to or larger than a value X_0 is

$$P(X \geq X_0) = 1 - e^{-e^{\alpha(x-x^-)}}$$

In which y is a dimensionless variable given by

$$Y = \alpha(x-a) \quad a = x^- - 0.45005$$

$$\alpha = 1.2825 / \sigma_x$$

$$\text{Thus } y = \frac{1.285(x-x^-)}{\sigma_x} + 0.577$$

Where x^- = mean and

σ_x = standard deviation of the variate X .

$$Y_p = -\ln[-\ln(1-P)]$$

Nothing that the return period $T=1/P$ and designating

$$Y_T = -\left[\ln \ln \frac{T}{T-1}\right]$$

The value of the variate X with a return period T is

$$X_T = x^- + K \sigma_x$$

$$\text{Where } K = \frac{(Y_T - Y_n)}{S_n}$$

In which Y_n = reduced mean, a function of sample size N is given in table in Van.T.Chow. book

S_n = reduced standard deviation, a function of sample size N is given in table in Van.T. Chow book

Table 5 Probability Analysis

year	Average depth of Rainfall	Decending order	order (m)	$Sx^2 = (x-x^-)^2$	Return period $T=(n+1)/m$	$Y_t = -(\ln \ln(T/(T-1)))$	Probability = $m/(N+1)$
1986	2075.0	3379.0	1	1510187	30.0	3.38	0.03
1987	1473.0	3032.0	2	777741.5	15.0	2.67	0.07
1988	3032.0	2906.0	3	571379.6	10.0	2.25	0.10
1989	1883.0	2721.0	4	325922.9	7.5	1.94	0.13
1990	2007.0	2598.0	5	200611.3	6.0	1.70	0.17
1991	2010.0	2544.0	6	155154.5	5.0	1.50	0.20
1992	2157.0	2530.0	7	144321.4	4.3	1.33	0.23
1993	2449.0	2467.0	8	100423.4	3.8	1.17	0.27
1994	3379.0	2449.0	9	89339.15	3.3	1.03	0.30
1995	1531.0	2357.0	10	42806.18	3.0	0.90	0.33
1996	1165.0	2278.0	11	16357.53	2.7	0.78	0.37
1997	1675.0	2222.0	12	5169.114	2.5	0.67	0.40
1998	2003.0	2208.0	13	3352.011	2.3	0.57	0.43
1999	1642.0	2157.0	14	47.56243	2.1	0.46	0.47
2000	2003.0	2075.0	15	5640.528	2.0	0.37	0.50
2001	1948.0	2010.0	16	19628.98	1.9	0.28	0.53
2002	1878.0	2007.0	17	20478.6	1.8	0.17	0.57
2003	2357.0	2003.0	18	21639.42	1.7	0.09	0.60
2004	2530.0	2003.0	19	21639.42	1.6	0.00	0.63
2005	2721.0	1948.0	20	40845.8	1.5	0.09	0.67
2006	2544.0	1883.0	21	71344.25	1.4	0.18	0.70
2007	2598.0	1878.0	22	74040.29	1.4	0.28	0.73
2008	2222.0	1719.0	23	185850.2	1.3	0.38	0.77
2009	1719.0	1675.0	24	225723.3	1.3	0.48	0.80
2010	2467.0	1642.0	25	258169.1	1.2	0.58	0.83
2011	2208.0	1531.0	26	383289.1	1.2	0.71	0.87
2012	1493.0	1493.0	27	431784.9	1.1	0.84	0.90
2013	2906.0	1473.0	28	458469.1	1.1	1.00	0.93
2014	2278.0	1165.0	29	970428.8	1.0	1.26	0.97
SUM		62353		7131785			
AVERAGE		2150.103					
S.D				504.6847			

Table 6 Computation of Expected Rainfall

Return period	$Y_t = -(\ln \ln(T/(T-1)))$	$K=(Y_t - Y_n)/S_n$	Expected Rainfall = $X_t = x^- + K.S_x$
2	0.36651292	-0.152252463	2073
5	1.499939	0.87014162	2589
10	2.250367	1.547056648	2931
25	3.198534	2.402339888	3363
50	3.901938	3.036837453	3683
100	4.600149	3.666650731	4001
200	5.2958121	4.294165704	4317
400	5.9902132	4.920542306	4633

Based on the methodology described above, the important parameters needed for the analysis were computed in Table 4 while Table 5 shows the depth of expected rainfall alongside their return periods. The results from the table shows that the expected rainfall for return periods of 2yrs, 5yrs, 10yrs, 25yrs, 50yrs, 100yrs, 200yrs and 400yrs are 2073.26mm, 2589.25mm, 2930.87mm, 3362.53mm, 3682.75mm, 4000.61mm, 4317.30mm and 4633.43mm respectively.

VII. MEAN ANNUAL RAINFALL

Gumbel distribution has the property which gives $T=2.33$ years for the average of the annual series. Thus the value of a Rainfall with $T=2.33$ years is called the mean

annual rainfall. As per above calculation, If the value of T is 2.33 than the expected rainfall will be 2170 mm.

Geomorphologic Information on Observed Floods”, Water SA 30 (3) 377-388

VIII. DECADAL RAINFALL

Year	Avg rainfall(mm)	Avg rainy days/year	Average days/year with heavy rainfall		
			Heavy rainfall (50-125 mm)	Very heavy rainfall (125 mm-250 mm)	Extremely heavy rainfall (>250)
1986 - 1995	440	78.2	99	29	4
1995 - 2005	398	76.9	87	24	4
2006 - 2015	438	79.6	76	21	3

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IX. CONCLUSION

From the Rainfall analysis carried out for Damanganga river basin 29 years annual average rainfall data rainfall shows that there is an increasing trend of the rainfall for all stations except Kelavani station which shows a decreasing trend. The average annual rainfall for the study period for the lower Damanganga basin is obtained as 2150 mm for the entire study period.

From the expected Rainfall analysis it is observed that as the return period increases, expected rainfall also increase. For the return period of 100 years, expected rainfall is 4000 mm. And mean annual rainfall is 2170 mm.

As per decadal analysis possibility of extremely heavy rainfall was occurred 3 days in the period between 2006-2015.

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